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Identify Novel Elements of Knowledge with Word Embedding

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Introduction

Novelty constitutes a core value in science (Bourdieu, 1975; Kuhn, 1970; Merton, 1973) and has broader impact on technological advancement (Kelly et al., 2021; Veugelers and Wang, 2019). As such, novelty serves as an important criterion for the assessment of scientific performance and for decision makings such as employment and funding allocation (Dasgupta and David, 1994; Merton, 1973; Stephan, 1996). It is therefore critical that scientific novelty can be reliably measured.

Though several bibliometric indicators for novelty have been proposed (Shibayama et al., 2021; Trapido, 2015; Uzzi et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2017), there remain a few fundamental limitations. First, most previous measures have not been validated. As novelty is a multifaceted concept, it is not entirely clear what aspect of novelty is captured or even whether novelty is measured at all. Second, the dominant approach of measuring novelty in previous studies appear to emphasize a specific type of novelty at the cost of overlooking other types. Namely, previous approaches mostly are based on the concept of *recombinant* novelty (Fleming, 2001; Simonton, 2003), with which a scientific document is considered novel if it includes a new or rare combination of knowledge elements (Dahlin and Behrens, 2005; Trapido, 2015; Uzzi et al., 2013; Wang et al., 2017). In contrast, few studies address the newness of a knowledge element itself (Azoulay et al., 2011). This is intriguing as the novelty of an element ("element novelty" hereafter), which serves as a building block of recombinant novelty, is conceptually and practically more fundamental (Ahuja and Lampert, 2001). This study thus aims to develop a validated approach to compute scientific novelty based on the element novelty concept.

Element novelty being underserved is attributed to a few technical challenges. One simple

approach to measure element novelty is to draw on text information and consider a document to be novel if it includes a new word (Azoulay et al., 2011). However, this approach faces a challenge when a document includes a new word that is merely a synonym of or similar to an existing word. Such an issue can be addressed by constructing controlled vocabulary dictionaries, but it requires substantial manual work and such efforts tend to be constrained within specific expertise areas.

To overcome these challenges, we developed a word embedding model that covers all scientific fields. Word embeddings allow us to quantify the distance between a pair of text data. Thus, we can measure distances between documents and thereby identify a *novel* document that is distant from other documents. To validate this novelty measure, we carried out a questionnaire survey, asking the authors of sampled scientific articles to self-evaluate multiple novelty aspects of the article they authored. We confirm that our novelty measure is correlated with the self-reported novelty of a knowledge element in various scientific fields. We further compare our novelty measure with a few previous novelty measures and demonstrate the advantage of our approach.

The contribution of this study is twofold. First, this is the first to provide a validated and field-universal approach to compute element novelty. Second, our word embedding model offers a technical basis to interpret scientific text information, which can be applied not only for calculating novelty but also for broader purposes.

This paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews previous novelty measures and technical backgrounds to compute novelty. Section 3 outlines the construction of the word embedding model and explains the operationalization of the novelty measure. Section 4 summarizes the results and the last section concludes.

Related Works

Measures of novelty

Given the multi-dimensionality of novelty, it is critical to understand what novelty aspect is captured by bibliometric novelty indicators, which has been insufficient due to limited validation efforts with a few exceptions. Nonetheless, previous measures are broadly categorized into two groups – recombinant novelty and element novelty – and thus might capture two aspects of novelty.

Recombinant novelty

Recombination as a source of novelty has been widely discussed in the literature. The creativity literature argues that associating remote elements is a path to creative solution in general as well as in science (Simonton, 2003; Uzzi et al., 2013). The management literature suggests that a novel invention results from a synthesis of diversified ideas and that combining components is a major route to technological innovation (Arthur, 2007; Fleming, 2001; Schumpeter, 2017). To operationalize this novelty concept, previous measures consider a document to be novel if it includes a new or rare combination of knowledge elements, in which a knowledge element is operationalized differently.

The most straightforward operationalization is to use a word as a knowledge element. For example, Zhang et al. (2021) measured the novelty of a scientific paper based on a new combination of keywords that appeared in the abstract. These approaches are intuitive, but the ambiguity of text information (e.g., synonyms) is a concern, which could be sorted out by a

controlled vocabulary dictionary.

Element novelty

The key limitation of recombinant novelty is that it overlooks the novelty of a knowledge element itself. Radically new ideas often have no discernible antecedent, and fundamental breakthroughs often result from exploring an uncharted knowledge space (Ahuja and Lampert, 2001). Such isolated incidents of novelty may not be captured by the recombinant novelty measures. In line with this notion, Ahuja and Lampert (2001) and Trajtenberg et al. (1992) measured the novelty of patents by considering a patent that has no reference to be novel, though this operationalization is not applicable to scientific documents.

A more generally applicable approach is to draw on the first appearance of a word(s) in a document. If a document includes a certain word or a sequence of words (N-gram) that is new to the world (e.g., the name of a previously unknown chemical compound), it can be inferred that the document delivers novel information. Arts et al. (2021) identified novel inventions based on the first occurrence of a word in patent documents. Though this is intuitive, the newness of a word can be misleading as it overlooks synonyms and similar words.

Word embedding

The word embedding technique addresses the limitations in the aforementioned approaches. By inferring the meaning of words from the context surrounding the word, the technique captures semantic relationships from unstructured text data and encodes it in a concise expression. It also reduces noises caused by synonyms and disciplinary jargons (Mikolov et al., 2013). Furthermore, a word embedding model can be extended to multiple languages. Importantly, the process of developing word embedding models requires little human intervention or expert knowledge.

Methodology

Training word embedding model

To develop a word-embedding model, we collected all scientific publications in English in the Science Citation Index Expanded (SCIE) from the Web of Science (WoS) database. We drew on 23 million (23,350,859) records with both titles and abstracts published between 1998 and 2018.

For each publication, we combined the title text and the abstract text and carried out a series of cleaning procedures with the Python library – Natural Language Toolkit (NLTK). Using a cleaned text in the 23 million documents as the training data, we developed the *word2vec* model on Python's Gensim package. As a result, we obtained 300-dimensional word vectors for 3,208,589 unique words. The median number of distinct words in a publication is 127.

Measuring Novelty

Based on the word embedding, we compute a series of element novelty measures in the following steps. First, we assign a vector to each document by simply taking the mean of the word vectors of all words included in the title and abstract text of the document. The document vector of document i is given by

$$v_i = \frac{1}{w_i} \sum_{k=1}^{w_i} v_{ik} \quad (2)$$

where $v_{ik} \in \mathbb{R}^{300}$ is a word vector of the k -th word and w_i is the number of words included in

document i .

Second, we compute the distance of all document pairs. The cosine distance between documents i and j is given by:

$$d_{ij} = 1 - \frac{v_i \cdot v_j}{|v_i||v_j|} \quad (3)$$

The cosine distance ranges from 0 to 2 with a larger value indicating a larger distance.

Finally, we compute the element novelty of each document. To measure the novelty of document i , we use the distances between document i and all other documents published before document i . Suppose that document i has N_i documents previously published. We sort all distance scores d_{ij} ($j = 1, \dots, N_i$) and use the q -percentile values as novelty scores ($ElementNovel_q$), where the 100-percentile is the maximum and the 0-percentile is the minimum. The intuition is that a document is considered novel if it is distant from other documents. Even if the minimum distance is still high, it indicates that the document is distant from all other documents. Therefore, low percentile values are of our interest. We compute a series of scores ($q \in [0,100]$) but mainly use the lower-percentile scores ($q = 0, 1, 5, 10, \dots$).

Questionnaire survey for validation

To test the validity of the proposed novelty measure, we conducted a questionnaire survey and draw on self-reported novelty scores. We sampled the respondents in the following steps. First, we identified contact authors whose email addresses are available in WoS publication records. We then selected contact authors who had published at least four English-written papers ("article", "letter", or "proceedings paper"). This is to ensure that the authors have sufficient research experience and can reasonably assess novelty. For each author, we selected one paper that was most recently published (as of 2018). To avoid recall bias we dropped authors whose latest paper was published in 2015 or before. Finally, we randomly sampled 10,357 author-paper pairs. After three waves requests, 1,020 were bounced back and 825 responses were collected (response rate = 8.8%). The scientific fields of the papers are biology (28%), chemistry (28%), medicine (13%), engineering (13%), physics (14%), and other fields (5%).¹

We developed the questionnaire items based on previous literature on scientific novelty (Dirk, 1999; Guetzkow et al., 2004) and tested them with a small-scale pilot survey. The items assess how the respondent's selected paper make contribution in three aspects: A) in creating/developing something (e.g., methods, materials, data, chemicals), B) in discovering/identifying something (e.g., phenomena, substances, molecules), and C) in understanding/explaining something (e.g., mechanisms, theories). Each aspect is assessed on a 3-point scale – "not applicable" (previously reported or irrelevant), "improved" (improvement over previously reported findings), and "novel" (not previously reported) (Figure 1). For the following validation we prepared three dummy variables ($Novel_A$, $Novel_B$ and $Novel_C$), each assigned 1 if the response is "novel" and 0 otherwise.

¹ There is no significant response bias in terms of scientific fields.

Figure 1. Survey Scores of Novelty.

Results

Figure 2 plots the correlation coefficients between element novelty measures and the survey novelty scores in three aspects. Although it presents the whole range ($q = [0,100]$) of element novelty measures, element novelty in lower q values is of our interest. The result indicates significant correlation between our element novelty measure and $Novel_B$ survey score ("discovering and identifying"). This is consistent with our expectation in that "discovery" and "identification" (e.g., phenomena, substances, molecules) tend to be represented by a word or relatively short expressions – i.e., literally elemental. In contrast, correlations with $Novel_C$ ("understanding and explaining") are largely insignificant. This is also understandable in that "understanding" and "explanation" (e.g., mechanisms, theories) are likely to be composite knowledge and less easy to capture in an isolated element. Interestingly, correlations with $Novel_A$ ("creating and developing") are negatively significant, though not very strongly (e.g., methods, materials, data, chemicals).

Figure 2. Correlation between Element Novelty Scores and Survey Scores.

Notes: N = 780. Pearson's correlation coefficient. * $p < 0.05$. ** $p < 0.01$. *** $p < 0.001$.

As the nature of novelty may differ across fields (Foster et al., 2021), we split this correlation analysis into five fields (Figure 3), finding somewhat different patterns between fields. First, the significant correlation with *Novel_B* ("discovering and identifying") is stable in all fields except engineering. A plausible explanation is that discovery or identification tends not to be the goal of engineering research, and thus, such contribution, even if it occurs, may not be as featured in engineering papers as in other fields. Second, *Novel_C* ("understanding and explaining") is largely insignificant except in medicine. This implies that new mechanisms and theories in medicine tend to be expressed in simpler terms. Third, *Novel_A* ("creating and developing") is found significantly negatively correlated in engineering and physics. This implies that new methods and materials in these fields tend to be closely related to existing knowledge.

Figure 3. Correlation between Element Novelty Scores and Survey Scores: Field Breakdown.

Notes: A series of element novelty scores ($q = 0, 1, 5, 10, 15,$ and 20) are displayed. Pearson's correlation coefficient. † $p < 0.1$. * $p < 0.05$. ** $p < 0.01$. *** $p < 0.001$.

Conclusions

As novelty is a core value in scientific advancement and technological progress, several bibliometric measures for novelty have been proposed. Nonetheless, a few fundamental limitations remain, which this study aims to address by offering a validated and field-universal approach to compute element novelty.

To this end, we first developed a word embedding model based on large-scale scientific text data. The word embedding technique draws on machine learning to extract semantic information from text data as high-dimensional vectors assigned to every word.

Second, using the developed word embedding model, we computed element novelty measures. The validation with our survey scores suggests that the proposed novelty measure is strongly correlated with *Novel_B* ("discovering and identifying") across most scientific fields. Therefore, our element novelty measure based on our own word embedding model seems to provide a strong approach to quantify element novelty in terms of discovering or identifying something new.

This study offers a few contributions. First, we provide a robust and versatile measure of element novelty. Despite its fundamental importance, element novelty has been underserved in comparison to recombinant novelty. Our approach based on word embeddings is robust and efficient in comparison to existing measures of element novelty based on keywords and manually developed controlled dictionaries.

Second, this study offers a platform to validate bibliometric novelty measures. Previous novelty measures were often not validated. As novelty is a multifaceted concept (Dirk, 1999; Guetzkow et al., 2004), it has been unclear what aspect of novelty is captured by previous measures. Our validation analyses clarify the novelty dimension our measure captures as well as its differences from other bibliometric measures.

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